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When Landscapes Inherit Loss: The Politics of Ecology in a Globalized World

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Abstract: *The paper entitled “When Landscapes Inherit Loss: The Politics of Ecology in a Globalized World” explores colonial and postcolonial exploitation of nature from an ecocritical perspective in Kiran Desai’s novel The Inheritance of Loss. The paper also dwells on the theory of ecocentrism to analyze the impact of neocolonialism and economic liberalization on man and nature with respect to migration and cultural alienation. Ecocriticism examines how human interaction with the natural world is portrayed in literary works. The novel explores individuals who are caught up in an ambivalent cultural and social ethos, and tries to demonstrate various forms of crises where environmental consciousness encounters with human greed and violence. The author talks about how human ways of life affect and have a huge impact on the environment. The novel clearly represents the fact that global capitalism is primarily defined by economic and environmental exploitation and the benefits of capitalist growth have been unequally divided, providing prosperity and progress to only a few people, while the majority is made to bear the brunt of its social, cultural and environmental consequences.*

Keywords: Ecocriticism, Ecology, Culture, Landscape, Nature, Globalization.

In *The Inheritance of Loss*, Kiran Desai portrays a community living in the North Eastern region of Kalimpong and delineates several crises faced by them in a post-colonial,

globalized world. The lives of these characters are affected by the uncertainties of local and global issues. Individuals having loyalties to Western ideologies struggle to make sense of the local community and their nature centered value systems. The human cost of globalization nullifies the soaring figures of economic gains achieved by a section of people as a result of economic liberalization. The setting of the novel is at Kalimpong, Sikkim, a North Eastern town situated in the foothills of Himalaya. The setting itself is symbolically representative of the depleting “Inheritance” of man as a result of human mistreatment towards nature. This is not only a threat to nature but all life forms are also treated the same way. The novel analyses in detail the imbalance that is created in nature as a result of modernity and economic liberalization. The scenic beauty of the place sets the mood of the novel. Desai’s description of the beauty of nature is evident from the beginning itself. She is intensely conscious of her environment and ecological sensitivity. Her environmental consciousness is evident from the novel’s opening sentences:

All day, the colors had been those of dusk, mist moving like a water creature across the great flanks of mountains possessed of ocean shadows and depths. Briefly visible above the vapor, Kanchenjunga was a far peak whittled out of ice, gathering the last of the light, a plume of snow blown high by the storms at its summit. (1)

The depiction of landscape reminisces a novelist narrating the features of a living character and shows how the novelist hold nature close to her heart as a living and breathing entity rather than a non-human background. Throughout the novel, the constant presence of nature influences and affects the characters in it. The mighty Kanchenjunga is symbolic of the power and supremacy of nature over man. The mountain stands tall as narrative unfolds and chaos erupts. All the characters are introduced against the remote location of Cho Oyu, a place famous for its breath-taking natural beauty:

Suddenly to the right, the Teesta River came leaping at them between white banks of sand. Space and sun crashed through the window. Reflections magnified and echoed the light, the river, each adding angles and colors to the other, and Sai became aware of the enormous space she was entering. By the river bank, wild water racing by, the late evening sun in polka dots through the trees, they parted company” (31).

The place evades the hustle and bustle of the city and is portrayed as a quiet place only to be destroyed by modernity and military insurgency. The peaceful backdrop set by the nature is perfectly used by the novelist to contrast with the ensuing chaos created by man. What once used to be a balanced ecosystem, where nature and humans coexist gets broken by the arrival of members of the Gorkha National Liberation Front (GNLF). They forcefully enter the Judge’s house and intimidate him, demanding food, housing, and one of his weapons. As Peter Barry puts it: “Nature really exists out there beyond ourselves, not needing to be ionized as a concept by enclosure within knowing inverted commas but actually present as an entity which affects us, and which we can affect, perhaps fatally, if we mistreat it” (252).

Love for nature lingers around in the form nostalgia. When the cook looks at the dried azalea and Juniper in the hut, he reminisces the day when they had burnt this incense all along the path on the arrival of Dalai Lama and Panchan Lamas in Kalimpong. He recollects the intense refreshing smell of incenses all around. He contrasts it with the choking smell of exhaust coming from the bus station. Author gives an indication that with progress and mechanical advancement, hostility towards nature too is on the rise. For the ecologically sensitive space where they inhabit, a hostile treatment of nature in the hands of human being adversely affects humans themselves and gives rise to various problems. As Sisir Kumar Ghose observes, when mechanization takes over, the laws of life are bound to be trampled upon (114).

Every time Gyan visits Cho Oyo to teach Sai, he is captivated by the beauty of nature:

He enjoyed the walk to Cho Oyu and experienced a refreshing and simple happiness, although it took him two hours uphill, from Bong Busti where he lived, the light shining through thick bamboo in starry, jumping chinks, imparting the feeling of liquid shimmering(67)

The concept of ecocentrism focuses on all the systems of the environment and their relative effect on the abiotic component. It is considered an umbrella concept that encompasses the environmental worldview and the geomorphological process and their effects (Albuhamdan et al.).It stresses on sustainable models of progress and development. Kiran Desai also advances an ecocentric perspective in her analysis of nature and characters. Ecocentrism underscores the inbuilt and intrinsic value of nature irrespective of the value given by human beings. It clearly states that ecology has got some intrinsic values irrespective of the acknowledgement of human beings. Ecocentrism is significant as it offers an essential solution to the environmental problems and it expands the concept of moral community in ethical terms. The idea also elucidates that societies have established moral sentiments in the field of ecology and this has improved their spiritual empowerment (Hasanthi). It also teaches modesty and simple living and thus is regarded as a suitable way to the achievement of sustainable environmental solutions. When the SDO looks at the beautiful flowering creeper in the garden of the judge, he says: “Beautiful Blossoms, Justice Sahib. If you see such a sight, you will know there is a God.” Though a power wielding authority, Judge loves and appreciates the beauty of nature and looks after his plants exactly as if they are babies (Desai 226). The reflection of SDO underscores the fact that in order to avoid the growing pandemonium in the life of modern man, it is necessary to rekindle his association with nature. The ethics of preserving nature for the sake of a better future is evident in these narratives.

For Sai, a girl without her parents, the judge's house cladded in nature offers the perfect refuge: "Kanchenjunga glowed macabre, trees stretched away on side, trunks pale, leaves black, and beyond, between the pillars of the trees, a path led to the house" (19). The building itself provides a picture of environmental sustainability and cohabitation with nature. Life there gifted her with the serenity that only nature can give: "Sai, sitting on the veranda, was reading an article about giant squid in an old National Geographic. Every now and then she looked up at Kanchenjunga, observed its wizard phosphorescence with a shiver" (1).

Systematic exploitation of nature is evident in the novel. Natural resources from Kalimpong forest stand overexploited. Indigenous products from the Kalimpong forest are consumed and sold to outsiders. The environmental exploitation has a direct connection with the rising insurgency in the region. The people are devoid of work and sustenance has been increasingly difficult. The residents are dissatisfied and left without a steady source of income.

People are fed up with government promises and increasingly begin to join armed rebellion. The rise of Gorkha National Liberation Front (GNLF) has direct connection with growing environmental degradation. People's activism reflects the principle of embodied ecology, where knowledge of the environment is inseparable from bodily experience. Rising insurgency becomes a platform where disadvantaged section of the society begins to express environmental knowledge and moral authority. Furthermore, their presence as minorities in the region underscore the importance of recognizing intersectionality—how gender, caste, ethnicity, and class intersect to shape experiences of environmental injustice (Shiva 22). An occurrence of over mining of stones from the river presented in the novel is another instance of environmental exploitation:

Every day the Lorries leave bearing away our forests, sold by foreigners to fill the pockets of foreigners. Every day

our stones are carried from the riverbed of the Teesta to build their houses and cities (159).

With globalization, the movement of people across the borders in search of work and better living conditions has increased tremendously. The United States, with its global supremacy, has become the preferred choice for many immigrants. Biju, the cook's son in *The Inheritance of Loss* makes several attempts to get a visa to the United States. For him, acquiring a visa to the United States turns out to be one of the hardest procedures in the immigration process. At the United States embassy, Biju witnesses the extent of the humiliation visa aspirants endure to be in the US:

Biju watched as the words were put forward to others with complete bluntness, with a fixed and unembarrassed eye—odd when asking such rude questions. Standing there, feeling the enormous measure of just how despised he was, he would have to reply in a smart yet humble manner. If he bumbled, tried too hard, seemed too cocky, became confused, if they didn't get what they wanted quickly and easily, he would be out. In this room, it was a fact accepted by all that Indians were willing to undergo any kind of humiliation to get into the States. You could heap rubbish on their heads and yet they would be begging to come crawling in...(*The Inheritance of Loss* 184)

Biju's father, the cook, believes that sending his son to the US would bring him social acceptability and material prosperity. The pathetic living condition in Cho Oyumakes the cook to think it as a better option to go abroad than indulging in the poverty and insurgency of the place. Emigration is perceived as a chance to elevate social rank, an opportunity to modify local hierarchies, seeking equality between different classes of people. The cook proudly proclaims that both he and the town's doctor have their sons in the US, a fact which puts him on equal terms with the "most distinguished personage in town" (Desai85). The cook's opinion of the US is in consonance with the popular image of the

country constructed by the media. He thinks of the US as a land of abundance: “In that country, there is enough food for everybody” and it is “the best country in the world” (85), and it is the land of “water and electricity” (24). Cook’s perception of his homeland underscores the stark and hopeless reality of the place.

Biju suffers a lot in the US because of his status as an illegal worker. He works for meagre pay in restaurants and undergoes gross human rights violation. Nostalgia strikes Biju at the sight of a dead insect in a sack of basmati rice. He craves to go home, but the words of his father counseling him not to return jerks him back to reality. Biju reflects that in India he could never afford basmati rice, and the incident gives him a chance for introspection with respect to his existence in the US. Santwana Haldar opines that:

In this age of globalization exile is often the chosen condition accepted for the hope of a ‘better life’ and when people are disappointed in such condition, the pangs of remaining far from homeland are heart-breaking (82).

When Biju’s American dream gets shattered, his love for his home village is rekindled. He thinks about the peaceful life of his village, the incredible taste of the roti cooked on a choolah, and the savour of fresh warm buffalo milk. According to Subha Mukerjee:

... people from different countries have settled in alien nations but their heart and soul are left behind in their far off motherlands. Physically the situation changes, but emotionally they hate everything alien (40).

The man’s association with nature and his locale is explained through the plight of Biju, the cook’s son. While Biju suffers the torments of an illegal immigrant in a foreign country, he remembers the blissful days he spent in his village. Nostalgic memories of his nature clad home soothe his tormented self. Biju calms and consoles himself by contemplating nature:

How peaceful our village is. How good the roti tastes there! It is because the Atta is ground by hand, not by machine ...and because it is made on a choolah, better than anything cooked on a gas or kerosene stove. Fresh roti, fresh butter, fresh milk still warm from the buffalo (103).

This reference exemplifies the beauty and simplicity of village life, where everything is unpolluted and genuine, a sharp contrast to his experiences in the United States. Nature instills him hope and positivity while facing inhuman treatments abroad. Biju has bright memories of his childhood in the village. Biju realizes the troubles of unsustainable progress and prosperity where man is a greater sufferer than nature.

Throughout the novel, novelist uses an ecocentric approach where the narrative is reinforced with the visible presence of diverse flora and fauna either directly or symbolically. The narrative is peppered with descriptions of wildlife and numerous descriptions of flora. Even the judge's dog Matt is presented as a character in this novel. Judge's cook is a worshipper of snakes and abhors killing them. As cook describes:

I went to the temple and they told me that I must ask forgiveness of the snakes. So I made a clay cobra and put it behind the water tank, made the area around it clean with cow dung, and did puja. Immediately the swelling went down (27).

There is a strong inclination for many characters to consume locally produced products than mass produced consumer goods. Father Booty is one such person. He owns a dairy farm and declares that cheese produced there is so much better than the mass produced Amul cheese which he considers as nothing more than a plastic wrapper: "This struck Father Booty as very funny, but he stopped laughing when they passed the Amul billboard, Utterly, Butterfly, Delicious, and Plastic! How can they call it butter and cheese? It's not. You could use it for waterproofing!" (Desai 208).

The inhabitants of Cho Oyulose their material possessions but reinstates their optimism for life that emanates from the

knowledge that love and family bonding entwined with their emotional connection with nature surpass the short-term happiness derived from material possessions. Seen in this light, Kiran Desai's work demonstrates her environmental sensitivity and emotional connection with nature.

Kanchenjunga is also called the Land of Flowers due to the abundance of flowering plants. The mountain also acts as a symbol for love and compassion. The story ends with another amazing depiction of Kanchenjunga, with a joyous scene where Biju finally comes home and embraces his father : "The five peaks of Kanchenjunga turned golden with the kind of luminous light that made you feel if briefly, that truth was apparent" (324).

The novel also reveals the life of Gyan, Sai's tutor belonging to the Gorkha community. Post independence, India witnessed nationalist affiliations giving way to sectarianism and regionalism, challenging the harmony and integrity of the nation. The Gorkha insurgency, which resulted from years of oppression and marginalization of the Gorkhas, challenged the peaceful life of the Anglophiles living in Kalimpong. Through insurgency, Gorkha separatists demanded a separate state for Gorkhas in the North East called 'Gorkhaland'. In the novel, the Gorkha rebels create an atmosphere of terror in the Kalimpong hills with their armed rebellion and acts of vandalism. The peaceful existence of the inhabitants gets interrupted by roadblocks, electricity cutoffs, and robbery. The Anglophiles in the locality become the primary targets of the insurgents because of their Western affiliations and insularity. In addition to abusing and humiliating the Westernized people, the insurgents start to vandalize and steal from their property.

The social and economic inequality between the Westernized Indians living in Kalimpong and the poor Gorkha community is evident in *The Inheritance of Loss*. The people of Nepali origin in the region belong to a disempowered and disadvantaged class. The community suffers from poverty and lack of education. Their feeling of separatism stems from the years of

marginalization. They feel cut off from mainstream India, and left out of the country's development trajectory. As a result, rebel organizations like The Gorkha National Liberation Front (GNLF) find following among young people of the Gorkha Community. The novel shows Gyan, inspired by the revolutionary rhetoric of GNLF leaders, joining the organization. Gyan is torn between two worlds – one of poverty and insecurity, and the other of progress and opportunity. By being part of the insurgent movement, Gyan gets a chance to discover himself, and an opportunity to find his self-worth and respect.

The affluent inhabitants of Cho Oyu rarely take notice of the economic inequality and discontent of their Gorkha neighbours till the resentment attains the proportion of a violent agitation. The novel underscores the failure of the consumerist way of life which prioritizes consumerist and material possessions over social and familial relations. Biju realizes the futility of his pursuit of material prosperity and decides to return home. He comes back to Kalimpong broken and penniless and happily reunites with his father. Sai and Gyan realize the need to be more sensitized towards the cultural differences around them. Overjoyed by the return of his pet dog, Mutt, the novel ends by revealing the humane side of the emotionally guarded Judge.

The Inheritance of Loss shows how individual lives are affected and transformed by larger socio-economic and environmental changes. The novel depicts the lived reality of characters existing in a world of fluid boundaries and cultural crossovers. The novel challenges the claim that economic liberalization and globalization create prosperity in the lives of people. While globalization has given opportunities for the people of the developed countries to be richer, political fragmentation, economic and environmental crisis push the people from the developing nations towards exploitation and indentured labour. The novel clearly represent the fact that global capitalism is primarily defined by economic and environmental exploitation and the benefits of capitalist growth have been unequally divided, providing prosperity and progress to only a few people, while the

majority is made to bear the brunt of its social, cultural and environmental consequences.

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